

8T and Hermitian Conjunction

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Abstract:

The following is an analysis of the Hermitian Conjunction idea by the new framework, 8T. The analysis will be done via the main equation and the coupling constant equation. The new framework is taking the difference between even amount of arbitrary variations and odd amounts of arbitrary variations, as the need for the conjunction and for the overall possibility of measurement.

Introduction

$$\frac{\partial L}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \frac{\partial L}{\partial s'} \frac{\partial s'}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g'} \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} = 0 \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{\partial g}{\partial t} = 0 \quad - \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} = 0 \quad (1.1)$$

$$\left[\frac{\partial L}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \right] \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} \delta g - \left[\frac{\partial L}{\partial s'} \frac{\partial s'}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g'} \right] \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} \delta g' = 0 \quad (1.2)$$

$$F_{V=0} = 8 + (1) \quad (2)$$

$$F_R\# = \left(8 * \prod_{V=1}^{V=R} N_V + (3) \right) + N_V = 30:128:850:9254.. \quad (2.1)$$

$$N_V = 2 \left(V + \frac{1}{2} \right); \quad V \geq 0 \quad (2.2)$$

$$N_V \in \mathbb{P} \bigoplus (+1); \quad \mathbb{P} \rightarrow \text{Set of Primes}$$

$$N_V = P_{max} \in [0, \mathbb{R}] \bigoplus (+1); \quad P_{max} \in \mathbb{P}$$

$$8 + (1): (24 + (3)) + 3: (120 + (3)) + 5: (840 + (3)) + 7 ...$$

$$(1): (30): (128): (850): (9254) ...$$

Suppose we would like to measure certain trait about a fermion, or fermion cluster in our matrix:

$$\sum_{i=1}^N \delta g_i = 0 \quad (3)$$

$$N \rightarrow \infty \quad (3.1)$$

$$N = 2n; \quad n \in \mathbb{R} \quad (3.11)$$

There is no limitation concerning such measurement, we have an even amount of arbitrary variations, which differ in sign and summed as zero. Suppose we had an odd amount of arbitrary variations.

$$N = 2n + 1; \quad n \in \mathbb{R}; \quad 2n + 1 \in \mathbb{C} \quad (3.2)$$

$$\sum_{i=1}^{N+1} \delta g_i \neq 0 \quad (3.3)$$

So now, the measurement of the fermion cluster become impossible as the manifold is no longer stationary. An elimination of that extra variation must be made. Nature can eliminate it by mirror projections, i.e. Hermitian conjugation. By doing so, the measurement of the fermion cluster will become possible again, or transitioned back to the real field from the complex field.

$$\sum_{i=1}^{N+1} \delta g_i + \sum_{i=1}^{N-1} \delta g_i = 0 \quad (4)$$

$$2n + 1 + 2n - 1 = 0 \quad (5)$$

So even amount of variation is measurement, additional variation causing the measurement to become impossible, and transition it to the complex field which makes the measurement impossible. To retain the previous state, a mirror projection will be taken.

$$2n \in \mathbb{R} \quad (6)$$

$$2n + 1 \in \mathbb{C} \quad (7)$$

$$2n + 1 + 2n - 1 \in \mathbb{R}; \quad (8)$$

Define Hermitian as:

$$\mathcal{H} : \mathbb{C} \rightarrow \mathbb{R} \quad (9)$$

References

- [1] O. Manor. "The 8- Theory – The Theory of Everything" In: (2021)